

Table 1: The studied germanosilicate zeolites

Zeolite	Framework	Organic compound used for the synthesis	Si/Ge molar ratio in the framework of		
			Synthesized materials	Hydrolytically unstable zeolite	Hydrolytically stable zeolite
*CTH	 >15				
IWW			1.0 – 5.0	<6	>13
UOV			1.3 – 3.3	<6	>13
UTL			3.7 – 6.0	<8	>18